

**Commentary to Gottfried “Does quantum mechanics
carry the seeds of its own destruction?” PHYSICS
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"I, for one, remain unpersuaded that a crisis of major proportions has been identified, but at the same time I am open to the possibility that such a crisis has been glimpsed, though perhaps only subliminally, by Bell and his great predecessors: Einstein, Schrödinger, de Broglie, Bohm and Wigner." Kurt Gottfried ([1], pg. 40)

Introduction

Quantum mechanics poses perhaps the most profound conceptual challenge in the history of science. Here we have a theory that has completely transformed the world, that threatens its destruction or perhaps its salvation, and yet at its core we are confronted with astounding and unrelenting apparent paradoxes. It is impossible to do justice to the volumes of research devoted to its many interpretations here. The first waves of discontent occurred during the 1920s at the famous Solvay conferences where Bohr and Einstein debated [2]. The eminent philosopher Karl Popper engaged with the early quantum theorists and criticized the Copenhagen interpretation for the first time in 1934 [3], and he remained engaged and critical for much of the rest of his life. Einstein too was of course never satisfied with the Copenhagen interpretation [4], and neither was Schrödinger [5]. There followed decades of what has been termed the “shut-up and calculate” epoch of physics (roughly from 1935 to 1980), where fundamental questions about quantum theory were discouraged as heresy. A second period of intense debate occurred in the wake of Bell’s theorem, and the subsequent experiments by John Clauser [6, 7, 8], Alain Aspect [9], and others confirming that quantum theory correctly describes the experimental results of spin correlated pairs of entangled particles. This cast severe doubt on the possibility that hidden-variable theories could be local. So this greatly tarnished the acceptability of models such as proposed by David Bohm [10, 11], stochastic models [12, 13, 14, 15], hydrodynamic models [16], or other de Broglie pilot wave theories [17]. These experiments were inspired by the seminal papers of Einstein, Podolsky, and Rosen [18], and of Bohm [19]. I think that even after

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Clauser's experiment Bell remained very dissatisfied with the Copenhagen picture. In particular he criticized the division by Bohr of the universe into a quantum world and a classical one which enabled or more accurately empowered an experimenter to perform a measurement on a quantum system and thereby seemingly cause a collapse of the wave function following the measurement by the mere act of observing the result [20]. This collapse was cast in mathematical granite by Von Neumann in his treatise on quantum mechanics as a projection operator acting on a quantum state vector in a Hilbert space [21]. Bohr's Copenhagen interpretation was bravely defended by legions of knights defending the ramparts over the decades. For them the Clauser experiment along with subsequent more precise experiments eliminating loopholes, were a vindication of Bohr. There was a debate between John Bell and Kurt Gottfried which succinctly illustrates the zeitgeist in the early 1990s [20, 1] This debate has continued and grown more intense since then. Today there is a cornucopia of ideas and interpretations of quantum mechanics vying for attention. It's clear that Einstein's and Popper's concerns about quantum theory are now recognized as relevant. Einstein's views on quantum mechanics were complicated and nuanced [22, 23]. He is commonly believed to be in favor of a local and realistic description underlying quantum mechanics. Most today believe that the Bell experiments rule out this possibility. In any event, he was not wrong in his desire to find a deeper explanation for quantum mechanics than the Copenhagen interpretation offered. To paraphrase a famous quote by Feynman, anybody who says that they understand quantum mechanics is fooling themselves, and nobody understands it. The mystery of quantum mechanics reminds one of the monolith in Kubrick's 2001 which is taken from Arthur C. Clark's Space Odyssey novels. We see its shape, but we don't see its core workings, structure, or origin.

Gottfried's defense of orthodoxy

Bell attacked Gottfried in his paper "Against Measurement" [20]. The disagreement was over the measurement problem. He argued that the concept of measurement implies, according to Bohr, a strict division between a "system" being measured and an "apparatus" doing the measuring. Bohr treated the measuring apparatus as classical, at least in part, so that it can be observed by an observer. Bell argued that this distinction is artificial and leads to conceptual difficulties. This division is sometimes called the "Heisenberg cut". Bell termed it the shifty-split. He thought that measurement should have no place in a physical theory. Gottfried explained that Bell wants a theory like classical electrodynamics that needs no measurement postulate and that the word 'measurement' should be banned. He illustrated his argument by reference to Gottfried's treatment of the measurement problem in [24].

Gottfried defended "the orthodoxy" in [1], which he described by these properties:

- I. The interpretation of the scalar product as a probability amplitude cannot be derived from the Schrödinger equation.
- II. A pure quantum state, represented by a ray in the Hilbert space, describes an ensemble of identically prepared systems.
- III. He agrees with Bell that the "apparatus" should not be treated as if it were not made of up of atoms and ruled by quantum mechanics. In this he differs from Bohr and

denies the existence of the Heisenberg cut

The second property is critical. Bohr postulated that a pure quantum state for a single particle was a complete description of that particle. Gottfried rather assumes that the wave function or Hilbert space ray describes an ensemble of similarly prepared particles, and not just a single particle. This ensemble assumption is called the statistical interpretation of quantum mechanics. Einstein was an advocate of this interpretation. Although this difference might seem rather minor, it has historically been a topic of great debate. If the wave function describes only an ensemble, it raises the question of what else is required to completely define a single particle within the ensemble. Because of this, Einstein argued that quantum mechanics was incomplete. This is discussed in Ballentine [25]. Here is a quote from this book (§6):

“The Statistical Interpretation, which regards quantum states as being descriptive of ensembles of similarly prepared systems, is completely open with respect to hidden variables. It does not demand them, but it makes the search for them entirely reasonable ... On the other hand, the Copenhagen Interpretation, which regards a state vector as an exhaustive description of an individual system, is antipathetic to the idea of hidden variables, since a more complete description than that provided by a state vector would contradict that interpretation”. Einstein is reputed to have written in a letter to Max Born that Bohm’s hidden variable theory was “too cheap”, but Bohm’s model is not the only possible hidden variable theory.

The Copenhagenists realized that the statistical interpretation of quantum mechanics greatly improved, if not fully resolved the measurement problem. Therefore they incorporated it into a modified Copenhagen interpretation, but accompanied this grafting with a fierce opposition to any suggestion that a deeper understanding of quantum mechanics was desirable or possible. This took its most vigorous form in their opposition to hidden variable theories. A good example of this movement is Léon Rosenfeld [26]. The interplay of Marxist philosophy, cold war politics, and the inherent intractability of quantum mechanics makes for a fascinating history with Rosenfeld at the eye of the storm in the 1950s. Bohm’s theory especially was in the crosshairs. I would say that Gottfried’s orthodoxy is very much in line with Rosenfeld.

Gottfried also makes a somewhat technical requirement of an acceptable measurement apparatus:

“If **A** is properly designed, it is an amplifier whose output is a superposition of states of the detecting systems, each of which has no overlap in configuration space (in this example, the space of the \mathbf{x}_m) with any of the others. To be more precise, if **O** is any observable related to the atomic centre-of-mass and/or the detectors, and if $\mathbf{m} \neq \mathbf{m}'$, the matrix element $\langle \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{x}_m | \mathbf{O} | \mathbf{R}', \mathbf{x}_{m'} \rangle$ is assumed to tend rapidly to zero when the separation between the coordinates in the bra and ket grows to macroscopic proportions. We call such observables macroscopically local. For any such **O** this apparatus has established a one-to-one correlation between the states of the micro-system **S** and macroscopically distinguishable states of the apparatus. If **A** cannot produce such an outcome it is a contraption, however useful or intriguing, that does not accomplish the measurement task, but such a failure would put no onus on quantum mechanics.”

The existence of such apparatuses are proven by experimental construction. They act

like a bridge between the microworld and the macro world. They take the place of the Heisenberg cut in the statistical interpretation and Gottfried's analysis. But, one might wonder if the existence of such apparatus can be proven from the unitary quantum evolution of the atoms that make them up alone, without resorting to experience. Perhaps it is due to this hint of circularity that prompted Gottfried to describe his analysis as a solution to the measurement problem FAPP. His arguments are similar to decoherence arguments, and as such may have the same problems as described in [27].

Gottfried illustrates his argument by considering an ensemble of neutral atoms passing through a Stern-Gerlach apparatus. He introduces a density matrix formalism to describe the system. This formalism mixes the classical probability elements in the apparatus with the quantum probability amplitudes. He argues that an initial pure state of atom plus apparatus is indistinguishable from a "butchered" density matrix with certain small interference terms set to exactly zero. It is by ignoring these "interference terms" in the density matrix that accomplishes the task of the Heisenberg cut in the Copenhagen interpretation. Bell objected to this crucial step in Gottfried's argument. He felt that it amounted to sweeping the Heisenberg cut under the rug. It has been suggested by Weinberg that the density matrix operator should be taken as the representative theoretical object for defining a state, rather than the Hilbert space vector [28, 29]. Gottfried's explanation of the measurement process in terms of density matrices is undoubtedly one of the best in the physics literature, and despite Bell's objections, deserves a prominent place in the historical development of the foundations of quantum mechanics. A review of the Bell-Gottfried debate is found in [30].

The revival of local hidden variable theories

Despite the results of the Bell experiments, research has continued on realistic hidden variable theories, ignoring the nonlocality implications. The ultimate loophole in the Bell experiments is the possibility that free will may not exist. The universe might be completely deterministic so that the random choice required in a Bell experiment cannot be truly random [31]. The most famous example of this idea is the cellular automata theory of Gerard 't Hooft [32]. A somewhat similar theory has also been proposed by Stephen Wolfram [33]. Just as a rising tide raises all ships, if the universe is governed by a superdeterministic algorithm, then a stochastic interpretation of the universe in terms of particles moving along stochastic trajectories could be an accurate picture of quantum phenomena. Just as a random walk can be simulated in terms of algorithmic random number generators, so too might the motions of particles be random walks whose trajectories are generated by the universe's cellular automata. Before getting carried away with this idea, we must keep in mind that there is no existence proof that such cellular automata algorithms exist, and certainly none have been found that can replicate the standard model of particle physics along with all the quantum phenomena. However, the possible existence of such algorithms gives a green light to research in stochastic models of quantum mechanics. A particularly large set of possible hidden variable models including Bohmian mechanics is given by generalized stochastic mechanics [15] (and references therein). Of necessity, a cellular automata describing our universe would obviously have to include what could be interpreted as

spontaneous wave function collapse. The game is afoot!

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